

ADJUSTMENT BEHAVIOUR AMONG ELEVENTH STANDARD STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Adjustment refers to the behavioral process of balancing conflicting needs, or needs challenged by obstacles in the environment. Humans and animals regularly adjust to their environment. Adjustment disorder occurs when there is an inability to make a normal adjustment to some need or stress in the environment. Successful adjustment is crucial to having a high quality of life. Those who are unable to adjust well are more likely to have clinical anxiety or depression, as well as experience feelings of hopelessness, difficulty concentrating, sleeping problems and reckless behavior. The present study reports on the level of adjustment behaviour possessed by the eleventh standard students and also the impact of independent variables on adjustment behaviour.

Key Words: Adjustment Behaviour, Eleventh Standard Students.

Need for the Study:

The purpose of education is to develop the whole some personality of the individuals. The person with integrated personality shows better adjustment in the society. A well adjusted person will always set realistic goals. The students studying in higher secondary are in the age group of 16 to 17 years. They are in the adolescence stage. These students experience conflicts in their minds regarding their bodily changes in this stage. They could not accept their sudden change in their systems. They are also having a maximum mental development. They can experience sudden spurt in emotional, social, intellectual, and sexual development. In this stage students find it difficult to adjust with their parents and the teachers in their school. The investigator noticed the adjustment problems of the adolescent students in the schools. This has made the investigator choose the present study which is entitled as "Adjustment Behaviour among Eleventh Standard Students".

Background of the Problem:

The complex structure and functioning of society proved to be too taxing for individual's adjusting capacities. Adjusting problems are increasing day-by-day and have challenged the parents, teachers as well as public. An individual is not born adjusted or maladjusted. So education helps people to adjust and to adopt himself to his own needs and demands of the society. If an individual could not adjust, he will have adverse effects on the learning and behaviour; this not only hinders him from doing whatever he is supposed to do at a particular moment but also sometimes leads to indiscipline and in some cases even to antisocial manifestation. Poor adjustment at home and school lead a student to perversion and juvenile delinquency. The higher secondary students face different problems at home, school and society at large. Hence the investigators decided to study the adjustment problem among eleventh standard students.

Terms and Definitions:

- **Adjustment Behaviour** - refers to adaptation and awareness of the individual faced with emotional, social and educational demands among the XI standard students.
- **XI standard students** - refer to the Students who are studying XI standard in Government, Aided and Private Schools under State Board Syllabus in Sivaganga District of Tamil Nadu.

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variables:

- Adjustment Behaviour

Independent (Population) Variables:

- Gender
- Religion
- Community
- Number of children in the family
- Group
- Medium
- School location
- School type
- School management
- Participation in sports and games

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the level of adjustment behaviour of the eleventh standard students.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in adjustment behaviour among eleventh standard students in terms of select independent variables.

Hypothesis of the Study:

- Select population variables exerts a significant influence on adjustment behaviour among Eleventh standard students

Methodology-In-Brief:

- Design : Descriptive
- Method : Normative
- Technique : Survey

Sample:

A stratified representative sample of 400 eleventh standard students constituted from higher secondary schools in Sivaganga District with due representation given to the variables, viz. Gender, Group, School Management and School Location.

Tools:

The tools used for data collection are as follows:

- Adjustment Behaviour Inventory [Standardized by Dr. A.K.P. Sinha and Dr.R.P. Singh (2000)]
- General Information Sheet structured by the investigator

Statistical Treatments:

The statistical treatments employed in the study are listed below.

- Test of significance of difference between the means of large independent samples.
- Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation ‘r’.

Adjustment Behaviour among Eleventh Standard Students:

The empirical average of Adjustment behaviour of the eleventh standard students involved in this study is found to be 123.70, while the theoretical average is 90 only. Thus the Adjustment behaviour of the eleventh standard students is found to be above the average level. In other words, Adjustment behaviour among the eleventh standard students is found to be high. This finding indicates that the eleventh standard students, in general possess better adjustment with others.

Adjustment Behaviour and Independent Variables:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of adjustment behaviour among eleventh standard students in terms of independent variables is presented in Table.

Table: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Adjustment Behaviour: Independent Variable – Wise

S.No	Variable	Sub-variables	N	M	SD	‘t’ - value	Significance At 0.05 level
1	Gender	Male	243	108.54	31.61	-12.33	Significant
		Female	147	145.92	27.34		
2	Religion	Hindu	276	116.69	35.37	-6.50	Significant
		Others	124	138.76	29.45		
3	Community	SC/ST	140	93.67	23.69	-16.04	Significant
		Others	260	137.82	30.437		
4	No. Of children in the family	Upto 2	290	117.70	35.38	-5.97	Significant
		3 and above	110	139.10	29.35		
5	Group studying	Bio-Maths	180	142.02	31.88	10.10	Significant
		Others	220	110.05	31.00		
6	Medium	Tamil	292	127.12	35.10	3.26	Significant
		English	108	114.63	33.64		
7	School locality	Rural	220	102.07	27.08	-13.14	Significant
		Urban	180	148.40	25.69		
8	School type	Unisex	184	94.60	22.46	-21.73	Significant
		Mixed	216	146.30	25.10		
9	School management	Govt./aided	291	122.66	36.05	-8.36	Significant
		Private	109	126.39	32.55		
10	Participation in sports and games	Yes	128	89.83	18.06	-18.54	Significant
		No	272	137.39	30.79		

Hypotheses Verification:

- Select population variables exerts a significant influence on adjustment behaviour among Eleventh standard students.
- It is revealed that all the ten variables used in the current study are found influencing eleventh standard students’ adjustment behaviour. Hence hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions arrived at from the study are listed below

- Adjustment behaviour of the Eleventh standard students is above the average level
- The Adjustment behaviour among the Eleventh standard students is found dependent on

- Gender
- Religion
- Community
- No. of children in the family
- Group
- Medium
- School locality
- School kind
- School management
- Participation in sports and games
- The Adjustment behaviour among the Eleventh standard students is found higher among the students
 - Who are female than male
 - Who are non-hindus than hindus
 - Who belong to other community than SC/ST
 - Who have 3 & above family children than those who have upto 2 family children
 - Who are studying Bio-maths group than other group
 - Who belong to Tamil medium than English
 - Who belong to urban schools than rural
 - Who belong to mixed schools than unisex
 - Who belong to private schools than Govt./Aided
 - Who do not participate in sports and games than those who participate in it.

Educational Implications:

This study states that adjustment behaviour among eleventh standard students is found low among the male students, those who are hindus, those who are other community students, those who are nuclear family, whose family have 5 and above children, those who are vegetarians, those who are studying arts group, those who are studying XII standard, those who belong to English medium, those who belong to rural schools, those who belong to unisex schools, those who are studying in government and aided schools, and those who are participate in sports and games. More programmes related to adjustment behaviour may be organized and counseling may be provided for the above said students will enhance adjustment behaviour on the part of the students.

Suggestions for Further Research:

Following are few areas of research related to the present investigation which deserve explorations:

- Replica of the present study may be conducted with the other districts
- Replica of the study may be conducted with other variables
- Replica of the study may be conducted with other standards
- Replica of the study may be conducted with the other systems like CBSE and ISC.

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